

The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Discipline Employee Work

¹ Bella Desi Kusumawardani, ² Sendi Satriadi

^{1,2} Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Gunadarma

Jl. Margonda Raya No.100, Depok 16424, Indonesia

belladk25@gmail.com, sendi_satria@staff.gunadarma.ac.id

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of the relationship between quality This study aims to analyze the relationship between job satisfaction and employee work discipline. The method used is a quantitative method with the subject of 130 operator employees or workers who directly hold the smooth running of machines in the company who work in production, maintenance, and utility, both men and women. The job satisfaction scale in this study was compiled based on aspects of job satisfaction according to Jewel and Siegall (1998) and the work discipline scale was prepared based on aspects of work discipline according to Amriyani (2004). The data analysis technique used is Karl Pearson's Product moment correlation with a bivariate correlation test. Based on the results of the analysis, an r of 0.301 was obtained with $p < 0.05$ which means that the hypothesis is accepted. The results show that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline where the higher the employee's job satisfaction, the better the employee's work discipline and vice versa the lower the employee's job satisfaction, the worse the employee's work discipline.

Keywords : Job Satisfaction, Work Discipline, Employee

Background of the Problem

In this era of globalization, many foreign companies invest their money or capital in Indonesia in the form of companies such as textiles, garments, residential property, and others. These companies compete with each other to produce the best quality so that buyers feel satisfied and the company gets a big profit and the company is looking for employees or employees who are experts in their fields. The number of companies that exist at this time many employees go in and out of one company to another, it is due to the lack of expertise they have, income that is not sufficient for their needs, work atmosphere that is not conducive or uncomfortable and so on. The element of human resources is needed and the most important thing in a company is human resources or employees because if there

are no human resources then the company will not run smoothly and if the selection of human resources is not done correctly in selecting employees then the company will not achieve its targets and the goals set by the company can be achieved. According to Ayu (2012) in every company there is usually a separate section that manages the field of employment and is commonly referred to as the personnel section, therefore it is the task of the personnel section which is responsible from recruiting employees to development in improving the quality of work to the dismissal of employees.

Employees are company assets because if there are no employees, the goods to be produced will not be finished, therefore employees who are serious in working will produce good quality goods. According to Ayu (2012) labour or employees are very important resources. Without a skilled and professional workforce, it is impossible for company activities to run well and smoothly. This

can be seen from the company's activities in achieving goals depending on the role of the labour used.

In every company all parts play an important role for the continuation of every job from one part to another is very influential and related, if one of the machines stops then the company cannot run smoothly as usual. There are several parts that are very important and influential in a company, namely the production section. For every company, production employees are a resource that is no less important than other company resources. In fact, production employees are in control of the production process. In other words, whether or not a production process runs smoothly will depend on the production employees (Muhaimin, 2004).

If an employee works with a pleasant feeling and there is satisfaction in him accompanied by a work environment, family friends and safe and comfortable facilities that he gets, the employee will work well. According to Siagian (in Widodo, 2015) argues that job satisfaction is a person's perspective, both positive and negative about his job. The company will progress, develop rapidly and achieve the goals that have been set is greatly influenced by the quality of the people or employees who work in it.

To strengthen the evidence that there is a relationship between job satisfaction and employee work discipline, according to Muhaimin (2004), in a study conducted at PT Primarindo Asia Infrastructure Tbk Bandung, a company engaged in the production of goods in the form of shoes, and the results of the study there is a significant positive relationship between employee job satisfaction and employee work discipline of shawing computer operator employees in production. The higher the employee job satisfaction, the better the employee work discipline and vice versa the lower the employee job satisfaction, the worse the employee work discipline.

Employee job satisfaction is influenced by needs, how far these needs have been met or not met. Therefore, the author is interested in conducting a study entitled "The relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline at PT Kondobo Textindo" in order to take more recent data and in a different place, namely at a textile company located in the Subang-West Java area with the same subject, namely operators, by taking random from several employees from each section, namely production, maintenance and utility.

Research objectives

This study aims to examine the relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline at PT Kondobo Textindo.

Definition of Job Satisfaction

Sutrisno (2009) states that job satisfaction is an employee's attitude towards work related to work situations, cooperation between employees, rewards received at work, and matters concerning physical and psychological factors. This attitude towards work is the result of a number of specific attitudes of individuals and individual social relationships outside of work, giving rise to a general attitude of individuals towards the work they face.

Aspects of Job Satisfaction

According to Jewell and Siegall (1998), there are several aspects in measuring job satisfaction:

- a. Psychological aspects
Related to the psychology of employees including interest, work peace, attitude towards work, talent and skills.
- b. Physical aspects
Related to the physical condition of the work environment and the physical condition of employees, including the type of work, work time arrangements, rest time arrangements, room conditions, air temperature, lighting, air

- exchange, employee health conditions and age.
- c. Social aspects
Relates to social interactions, both between fellow employees and superiors and between employees of different types of work and relationships with family members.
 - d. Financial aspect
Relates to the security and welfare of employees, which includes the system and amount of salary, social security, benefits, facilities and promotions.

Definition of Work Discipline

According to Rivai (2004) work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change a behaviour and as an effort to increase a person's awareness and willingness to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms.

Aspects of Work Discipline Measurement

Amriyani (2004) concluded that the aspects of work discipline include:

- a. Obedience to orders
Compliance occurs when a person does what he is told.
- b. Working time
Working time as the period of time during which the worker concerned must be present to start work and he may leave work.
- c. Compliance with rules
A set of rules that the group in the organisation has may be a pressure for a person or employee to comply.
- d. Careful use of uniforms or work tools
Every employee, especially in a work environment, receives a uniform every two years.

Definition of Employee

According to MacMillan (in Rachmawati, 2008) employees are people who are paid regularly to work for someone or a company.

Employees are people who have obligations and rights, which arise as a consequence of the employment relationship, namely the relationship between employees and employers or companies in terms of employment. Both parties have entered into an agreement to enter into an agreement, either written or oral, either individually or jointly regarding work according to Mulianto (2011).

The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Employee Work Discipline

According to Ayu (2012) labour or employees are very important resources. Without a skilled and professional workforce, it is impossible for company activities to run well and smoothly. This can be seen from the company's activities in achieving goals that are highly dependent on the role of the workforce used.

Hypothesis

The hypothesis in this study is that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline at PT Kondobo Textindo, the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the work discipline of employees and vice versa, the lower the job satisfaction, the lower the work discipline of employees.

Normality Test

For the normality test, the SPSS 20.0 for windows programme tool is used, namely the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to test the normality of the aitem distribution.

Based on normality testing on the work discipline variable has a significance of 0.000 and on the job satisfaction variable has a significance of 0.200. Then it can be said that the distribution of items on the work discipline scale is abnormally distributed because it is less than 0.05 and job satisfaction is normally distributed

because it is more than 0.05. The test results can be seen in table 7 below:

Linearity Test

Based on linearity testing on work discipline variables with job satisfaction has a significance of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$). This shows that there is a linear (direct) relationship between the variable and the variable job satisfaction in operator employees, because the significance value of the two variables is less than 0.05.

Hypothesis Test

Based on the results of the correlation analysis, it is found that there is a significant relationship between work discipline and job satisfaction with a significance value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$), and the correlation coefficient (R) value of 0.301 which indicates that there is a positive relationship between work discipline and job satisfaction because the R value is close to +1. Thus, the hypothesis in this study is accepted, that there is indeed a relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline.

Statistical Description

Based on the results of descriptive statistics, it is known that the average score of work discipline of 130 operator employees is 69.88 with a standard deviation of 6.676, and the average score of job satisfaction is 116.98 with a standard deviation of 9.652. The maximum and minimum scores for work discipline are 88 and 58, and the maximum and minimum scores for job satisfaction are 142 and 91.

Work discipline

The number of well-discriminated items on the work discipline scale is 21 items using a score criterion of 1 to 4, this means the smallest score is 1 and the

largest score is 4. The minimum total score is the smallest score multiplied by the number of well-discriminated items ($1 \times 21 = 21$), then it can also be known that the maximum total score is the largest score multiplied by the number of well-discriminated items ($4 \times 21 = 84$), so that a range of 21 to 84 is obtained with a distribution distance of $84 - 21 = 63$, thus the standard deviation is $63 \div 6 = 10.5$. score 6 is obtained from a normal distribution curve which is divided into 6 regions, namely 3 positive areas and 3 negative areas. After getting the standard deviation, then find the hypothetical mean by multiplying the middle score on the scale score by the number of well-discriminated items ($2.5 \times 21 = 52.5$). The score of 2.5 is obtained from the median or middle score of the score criteria used between 1 and 4, namely 2.5.

Job satisfaction

The number of well-discriminated items on the job satisfaction scale is 31 items using the score criteria of 1 to 4, this means that the smallest score is 1 and the largest score is 4. The minimum total score is the smallest score multiplied by the number of well-discriminated items ($1 \times 31 = 31$), then it can also be known that the maximum total score is the largest score multiplied by the number of well-discriminated items ($4 \times 31 = 124$), so that a range of 31 to 124 is obtained with a distribution distance of $124 - 31 = 93$, thus the standard deviation is $93 \div 6 = 15.5$. The score of 6 is obtained from the normal distribution curve which is divided into 6 regions, namely 3 positive regions and 3 negative regions. After getting the standard deviation, then find the hypothetical mean by multiplying the middle score on the scale score by the number of well-discriminated items ($2.5 \times 31 = 77.5$). The score of 2.5 is obtained from the median or middle score of the score criteria used between 1 and 4, namely 2.5.

Discussion

This study aims to empirically test the relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline at PT Kondobo Textindo. Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out, it shows that the hypothesis that has been formulated is accepted, which means that there is a positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline at PT Kondobo Textindo. The existence of a relationship or accepted hypothesis can be seen in the bivariate correlation table above with a significance level of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$), so the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline at PT Kondobo Textindo (0.301), shows that the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the work discipline.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it can be seen that the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted, namely that there is a very significant relationship between job satisfaction and employee discipline at PT Kondobo Textindo which is positive. This means that the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the work discipline of employees. Conversely, the lower the level of job satisfaction, the lower the work discipline of employees at PT Kondobo Textindo.

Based on descriptive analysis, it is known that most of the samples have very high work discipline. This can be possible because employees have job satisfaction and good working time as a period of time when the worker concerned must be present to start work and compliance with regulations between employees and superiors.

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